

STRATEGIES OF VOCABULARY REINFORCEMENT FOR ADULT LEARNERS

Otabekova S.O.

Master's student, Alfraganus University

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Abstract. *The need to replenish vocabulary is determined by various reasons. The surrounding life, studying in college, reading books, newspapers, magazines, listening to the radio, watching television programs enrich children's knowledge, along with which unfamiliar words often come. Among the unfamiliar words there may be those that should not be used because of their rude, vulgar meaning. The teacher's task is to help students master that part of the passive vocabulary that is acceptable when communicating.*

Despite the fact that Russian is the native language for most children and they speak it from birth, few can express ideas correctly, clearly, and concisely. This leads to the second task facing the teacher - to teach how to use the existing vocabulary with maximum benefit.

This work presents exercises that can be used to enrich vocabulary and teach the ability to use known and newly acquired words. These exercises are applicable not only in lessons devoted to the direct study of vocabulary as a branch of the science of language, but also in lessons on various topics.

Keywords: *need, vocabulary, surrounding life, studying in college, reading books, newspapers, magazines, listening to the radio, watching television enrich children's knowledge.*

A person's vocabulary consists of active and passive vocabulary of the national language. An active vocabulary is the words whose meaning a person knows and uses in speech every day in one or another area of communication. Passive vocabulary - words whose lexical meaning a person understands in general terms and rarely uses in speech. The boundary between active and passive stock is fuzzy and fluid. For example, the word flash drive quickly moved from neologisms (words that are just beginning to live in a language and are not known to a large number of its speakers) into the active stock of Russian speakers. Sources for replenishing an individual's speech are the speech of others, the media, literature, language courses, dictionaries.

According to language researchers, the vocabulary of a 6-7-year-old child is from 3 to 7 thousand words, the vocabulary of a 10-year-old child moving from primary school to secondary school is from 7 to 12 thousand words, for a high school student and an adult - from 25 to 70 thousand words. It is noteworthy that the ratio of active and passive vocabulary is different for people of different ages: in a preschool child the passive vocabulary is minimal, in a high school student and an adult it significantly exceeds the active vocabulary. It has been proven that the vocabulary of a middle school student is replenished with 6-8 new words every day, and the vocabulary of a high school student is replenished with 7-12 new words.[1].

Enrichment of vocabulary is aimed at ensuring that when generating speech, the student has free contextual substitution of words to clarify thoughts, eliminate repetitions, create imagery and stylistic norms. When perceiving text, a rich vocabulary allows you to adequately perceive information not only through understanding the dictionary meanings of words, but also their connotations. The enrichment of the dictionary occurs through the introduction into the linguistic

consciousness of thematic groups of words, synonymous series (including phraseological units), antonymic pairs, which allow making the choice of the necessary unit.

The main aspect of work to enrich students' vocabulary is work on the meaning (system of meanings) and use of the word. At the same time, it is necessary to know that the child's ability to adequately perceive and interpret words of abstract semantics is gradually formed. Primary school and 5th-6th grade students are not capable of independently interpreting abstract words and explain their meaning by pointing to the situation in which this sign is manifested (for example: joy is when friends meet). The teacher must pay special attention to the interpretation of words, ensuring its adequacy and developing the linguistic sense of students. The richness and expressiveness of speech is also enhanced by understanding the lexical compatibility of words, the possibility of using various means of expression in speech (metaphors, comparisons, antithesis and other tropes)[2].

In vocabulary work, the following types of exercises are distinguished:

1) an explanation of the lexical meaning (system of meanings) of a word in the form of an isolated logical interpretation given in the text of a textbook, dictionary or oral explanation of a teacher, or a synonymous series;

2) compiling thematic groups of words with the identification of synonymous, antonymic, derivational (word-forming) and generic connections;

3) analysis of lexical means of an exemplary or negative (intentionally non-exemplary) text;

4) determining the functions of using a lexical unit in a text (for example, a synonymous series);

5) editorial correction of negative text;

6) composing phrases, sentences, text.

English methodologist Andrew Walkley said: "Without grammar you can say little, without vocabulary you can say nothing." One cannot but agree with this statement. Without denying the importance of studying grammar, we understand that much more meaning is contained in words, rather than in grammatical structures.

Enriching students' vocabulary is the most important task of a foreign language teacher. There are two goals for enriching vocabulary:

- quantitative increase in words and qualitative improvement of the existing vocabulary;
- learning the ability to use known and newly acquired words.

We try to realize both of these goals in our lessons.

The main problem of learning vocabulary is the retention of all introduced and fixed words in the students' memory, right up to the end of school (we can practically talk about 80% of words, minimum – 60%. This requires repeated (over 20 times) use of each of them for a long time at optimal intervals (from 1–3 days at the beginning of the organized use of the word to 1–3 months at the end of this period). The organization of 90% of such repeated uses of passive vocabulary and 30–50% of active vocabulary lies with the author of the textbook. However, more than half of the repetitions of active vocabulary. and about 10% of repetitions of passive vocabulary should be provided by the teacher during speaking in the lesson. To do this, the teacher must include in the project of each lesson a list of not only new, but also words repeated in it (poorly learned, not used for a long time, in need of reinforcement). There are a variety of ways to enrich students' vocabulary. Here are some strategies to help you achieve this [5-6].

Lexical games

They are situational and variable exercises in which an opportunity is created for repeated repetition of a speech pattern in conditions close to real speech communication with its inherent characteristics - emotionality, spontaneity and targeted influence. Lexical games focus students' attention on lexical material, aiming to help them acquire and expand their vocabulary, illustrate and practice the use of words in communication situations. Lexically focused exercises in the form of a game contribute to the development of students' attention, their cognitive interest, and help create a favorable psychological climate in the lesson.

Memory game: The teacher writes words or phrases on the board that need to be reinforced. The teacher asks you to turn away or close your eyes and erases one LE. Students must guess which LE is missing and write it down correctly on the board [7].

Snowball game: starting the game, the teacher says the first word. Each subsequent student must name all the previous words in the order in which they were included in the game and say a new word. If someone forgets a word or mixes up the order, he is eliminated from the game.

Team game: students are divided into two teams, a student from the first team names a word in English, students from the other team must name this word in English as quickly as possible and get a point for it. The game lasts 5 minutes. The team with the most points wins.

Forbidden words

“Banned words” are simply words that students should not use in their work. Make your list of "banned" words - these are simple words that your students use over and over again when they could use more complex vocabulary (for example, like, interesting, boring, good, nice, bad, big, run, etc.)

However, take a minute to discuss the “allowed” synonyms for each of these words, discussing the nuances of meaning. A great idea would be to make a poster with a “banned” word and its alternatives. For example: Interesting: amusing, enjoyable, entertaining, fascinating, gripping, absorbing, newsworthy, arresting, captivating, exceptional, magnetic, etc. Don't forget to discuss the stylistic features of synonyms.

"Vocabulary family"

Imagine that you have a choice: your students can learn 1 word or 5 at once. Which would you prefer? Naturally, we want our students to learn as much as possible when it comes to vocabulary. One way to achieve this is to introduce vocabulary through related words or “word families.” Instead of one verb depend, your students will be familiar with dependence, dependent, independence, independent. At the same time, we will get acquainted with the methods of word formation.

Graphic organizer

Draw an A4 sheet of paper into four rectangles. At the intersection of these lines, write the word or phrase you want to remember. Label each rectangle, starting from the top left, clockwise:

Description: Define the term using your own words.

Characteristics: Give at least 3 interesting characteristics of the term.

Synonym: What is it like?

Antonym: What is it not like?

Students use their vocabulary to fill in the rectangles. They are supplemented with drawings or diagrams.[10].

The Graphic Organizer memorization method helps students learn new words. If you define new lexical units in your own words, give examples from familiar situations and visual images, then any word will be imprinted in your memory for a long time.

How to use a graphic organizer in the classroom:

Preparation. Determine a list of words to study within a specific topic. Working with a group of 3-4 students, assign each group to study one word.

Mini-demonstration. Explain to the class what a graphic organizer is and how to fill in the spaces.

Group work. Make it easier for students to work on new words by discussing the word given to them with each group. Use leading questions to get the group thinking in the way you want.

Discussion in class. Give the task to one student from the group to present their word. Allow members of different teams to communicate with each other and become familiar with other words. This will take 2-3 minutes so as not to interrupt the rhythm of the lesson.

Using dictionaries.

Learning a new LE always starts with a dictionary. Currently, it is more convenient to use electronic dictionaries to work with new LEs, because they not only significantly exceed book ones in volume, but also find the desired word or phrase in a few seconds; electronic dictionaries contain a larger number of neologisms, since language is a reflection of the real life of people, their culture. All new vocabulary cannot be adequately reflected in “paper” dictionaries for the simple reason that they take too long to develop. In fact, many dictionaries that were formed in the linguistic atmosphere of the mid-century are very outdated. They do not provide modern meanings of old words, and many new words are simply missing. This has become especially obvious with the development of the Internet: most Web pages consist of English texts written in a lively modern language using colloquial vocabulary and slang. This problem can only be solved by using electronic dictionaries. Massive software products, such as electronic dictionaries, are characterized by frequent changes of versions and constant feedback from thousands of users.[9] Electronic dictionaries not only contain transcriptions, but can also pronounce words.

The most common are ABBY Lingvo, Multilex, Multitran, Cambridge Dictionaries Online. I would like to introduce you to the following site <http://wordsteps.com>, it allows you to do work similar to working with your dictionary (Vocabulary). Click on the “create a new dictionary” button, give it a name, enter words and translations into special fields, and the program creates exercises. There are several types of exercises, for example, multiple choice, forming a word from letters, and performance statistics. You can use thematic dictionaries already compiled by other people. There are word limits in the free version.

"Wall of Words"

The effectiveness of learning depends on the effectiveness of the learning environment, and the classroom, as part of such an environment, plays an important role. Invite your students to become active participants in vocabulary development with the Word Wall. Ask students to write down new words that they encounter in their out-of-school life. The word should be written on a small card, with a definition and example on the back, and the card should be placed on the “Word Wall.” Every student can become familiar with words. After some time, you can ask students to come up with and play games with their classmates with these words (Crosswords, Deaf Phone, Field of Miracles, etc.). Students usually like that they “had a hand in”, and such words are remembered better.[11].

Flash cards

Cards should be easy to use. It is necessary to choose the right size for cards that will fit comfortably in the palm of your hand and that will be easy to transfer.

Thick paper or cardboard is used for cards; you can laminate the cards for longer use.

A word in a foreign language is placed on the front side of the card; it is possible to add a transcription and an example of using the word in a sentence. On the reverse side there is a picture or translation indicating the lexical meaning of the word.

Using flash cards is an effective method for:

Studying the graphic form of words

Memorizing lexical meaning

Rapid speech reproduction of a word (reading)

The transition of words from passive vocabulary to active (use in speaking)

Increasing motivation to learn a foreign language.

In the 70s of the 20th century, the German scientist and journalist Sebastian Leitner proposed a practical method for learning words (and in our case we are talking about foreign vocabulary) with less effort than the traditional method - the method of simply repeating flash cards, constantly turning over one after another.

In this method, so-called flash cards are sorted into groups based on how well the student has mastered the information on each card. For example, when learning a foreign language, a student tries to remember the meaning of a word written on a flash card. If he remembers it, then the card is moved to the next group. If not, then the card is returned to the first group. Each subsequent group is repeated at increasing intervals. Advantage of the method

So, according to Leitner's system, you repeat more often those words that are more difficult to remember, which allows you to save time on words that are remembered well. The result is a reduction in time spent on training.

Adapted method of the Leitner system - you need to take a stack of flash cards. If the word on the top card is known, then the card is moved to the end of the pile. If a word is unknown, then after viewing the translation it is moved to the middle of the pile (closer to the beginning) so that it appears earlier and more often than words already known. Thus, we achieve more frequent repetition of the necessary difficult vocabulary and its strong memorization.

Memory cards

The Mind Map is an alternative to traditional methods of processing and transmitting information (notes, short notes, diagrams, etc.). This alternative is more productive, as it has a natural psychological basis, and most importantly, turns the student into an active creator of his own knowledge.

The psychological basis of the memory map method is associative thinking. The memory map itself, from the point of view of its creators, is a model of how our brain works.

It is enough to reproduce in memory one object of this information map, and in a chain it will pull along dozens of interconnected facts, events, and sensations. This is how multidimensional associative thinking arises, which allows you to see not just an object in the surrounding world by itself, but in connection with other objects.

This is the principle of operation of a memory card.

There are certain rules for creating mind maps developed by Tony Buzan, which are described in detail in his book "How to Mind Map", namely:

The main idea, problem or word is located in the center. Buzan attaches almost the main importance to highlighting the keyword of the associative chain

To depict the central idea, you can use drawings and pictures.

Each main branch has its own color.

Only colored pencils, markers, etc. are used to create maps.

The main branches are connected to the central idea, and the branches of the second, third, etc. order are connected to the main branches.

The branches should be curved, not straight (like tree branches).

Only one keyword is written above each line-branch.

For better memorization and assimilation, it is advisable to use drawings, pictures, associations about each word.

The result of the work is an individual product of one person or one group. Expresses individual capabilities, creates space for the manifestation of creative abilities.[12].

You can, of course, use special programs for creating a Mind Map, such as MindJet Mind Manager, ConceptDraw MINDMAP, MindMapper, etc., but I recommend creating mind maps with your hands - this is a good way to take your mind off the computer and train your thinking and imagination.

Benefits of Mind Maps

easy to use

show connections between phenomena, logic of thinking

contribute to better memorization of information

collect large amounts of data

develop creativity and thinking

This technique is good to use in group work at the stage of consolidating the lexical material covered on a certain topic.

Rhymes, poems, songs

The study of lexical units takes place in a playful way, which contributes to the students' comfortable state in the lesson. Children usually have unstable attention. Therefore, it is imperative that the lesson plan includes types of work that relieve tension, redirect children's attention, and evoke a positive emotional mood. Learning rhymes and poems corresponds to the age and psychological characteristics of children. They are easy to learn and have such characteristics as rhythm and sound repetition. Children enjoy learning poetry. And what is experienced emotionally positively remains in the memory for a long time, leaving a mark in the child's consciousness. Thanks to rhyme, lexical and grammatical structures are easily activated in oral speech.[13].

The fundamental point here is the use of an authentic speech sample, and here songs and poems have many advantages over prose material. They are easy to introduce, easy to remember, and can be sung in chorus, which takes the psychological pressure off students who lack self-confidence. In genuine song material, there are often whole phrases and individual lexical units that are characteristic specifically of colloquial speech.

Crossword

Crossword puzzles are a great way for students to enhance their vocabulary.

This strategy can be used in the first lesson of a new topic. Students remember words they will use in future lessons.

A crossword puzzle is a great way to review what you have previously learned before a test. Invite students to create a crossword using new words from the topic they have studied. They will repeat their spelling and remember the meanings. For weaker students, you can attach a thematic list of words to the crossword puzzle so that they can choose the appropriate ones.

Of course, the list of strategies for expanding students' vocabulary can be continued, and each teacher will choose those techniques that are closer to him. The main thing to remember is that work on vocabulary should be constant and systematic.

Currently, tests occupy a very important place in the process of learning a foreign language. There are several reasons for this.

Firstly, in connection with the preparation of students for passing international exams and the Unified State Examination, there is a need for constant training in performing various tests, which will help students “get their hands on” in this type of activity and successfully cope with exam tests.

Secondly, tests, being a relatively new type of educational activity, often replace many exercises (“drills”) and become an effective means of increasing student motivation. Using tests in the classroom and at home helps students develop new goals and interests. The positive emotions that students receive from the knowledge of a correctly completed test have a very beneficial effect on the entire educational process.[3].

Thirdly, working with tests involves the student’s involvement in active mental activity, since by comparing and analyzing various language structures in tests, students thereby perform complex verbal and mental operations. This, first of all, relates to the development of linguistic conjecture, without which real communication is impossible.

And finally, tests are a very economical type of educational activity, since they do not take much time to complete. They can be done individually, in pairs or as a whole group.

Meeting all the basic psychological and didactic principles, tests are increasingly used in the study of foreign languages. However, too much emphasis is placed on so-called “control” tests and the possibility of using educational and training tests is often ignored. This, in particular, concerns the work on introducing and consolidating vocabulary.

A good example of educational and practice tests is the series "English Vocabulary in Use" by Michael McCarthy, Felicity O'Dell, Cambridge University Press. The entire series of the complex is designed in such a way that the left side of the page spread clearly explains a certain linguistic phenomenon, while on the right there are tests to consolidate it.[11].

If we turn to the semantization of new vocabulary, then, as many methodologists claim, the advantage of the non-translation method is obvious. Semantization using various methods of word formation allows you to introduce a word into a certain paradigm, which contributes to the establishment of stronger paradigmatic connections of a given word, as well as the repetition of already learned words that are included in this category. The development of the ability to guess a word based on its individual elements is associated with the combinatorial abilities of students. “The latter can be improved by systematic work on completing words in their parts and on filling in the missing elements of a phrase.”] Guessing from context, definition and semantization with the help of synonyms and antonyms certainly helps not only to a deeper understanding of the meaning of a word, but also to the expansion the total vocabulary of students.

Stages of completing the task:

Determine what part of speech is needed to fill in the gap.

Remember the parts of speech characteristic of this part of speech.

Determine from the context whether the word has a positive or negative meaning.

Such tests make it possible to study and consolidate word formation methods, being a very effective means for expanding students' vocabulary.

Thus, we can conclude that the above types of test tasks are an effective means of learning a foreign language, since they contribute to the intensification of the speech-thinking process, helping to expand and deepen the active and passive vocabulary of students.

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